

SCIENCE GOALS, DESIGN, AND PERFORMANCE OF AN ORBITAL ULTRA-COMPACT IMAGING SPECTROMETER FOR THE MOON (UCIS-MOON). A.A. Fraeman¹, B.L. Ehlmann², N. Bowles³, D.R. Thompson¹, R.O. Green¹, K. A. Shirley³, B.W. Denevi⁴, R.L. Klima⁴, A.M. Dapremont⁴, C.S. Edwards⁵, K.L. Donaldson Hanna⁶, ¹Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, ²Laboratory for Atmospheric & Space Physics & University of Colorado, Boulder, ³University of Oxford, ⁴Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory, ⁵Northern Arizona University, ⁶University of Central Florida

Introduction: NASA recently selected the Ultra-Compact Imaging Spectrometer for the Moon (UCIS-Moon) for a flight opportunity on a future commercial lunar orbiter [1]. The instrument will measure reflected and emitted radiance from the lunar surface between 0.6 – 3.6 micrometers at 10 nm spectral sampling. These data will provide the highest spatial resolution maps to date collected of water and minerals on the lunar surface.

Design and Heritage: UCIS-Moon is a sister instrument to the High-resolution Volatiles and Minerals Moon Mapper (HVM³) imaging spectrometer that flew on the Lunar Trailblazer mission [2-4]. UCIS-Moon was a technology demonstration instrument originally developed for a lunar lander or rover through NASA’s Development and Advancement of Lunar Instrumentation (DALI) program. HVM³ was developed by the same team in parallel for an orbiter, and the two instruments share a common spectrometer design and performance specifications (Figure 1, Table 1). UCIS-Moon adapted for orbit will utilize most aspects of the HVM³ design, enabling it to be able detect 100 – 1000 ppm water ice even in permanently shadowed regions at the lunar poles, identical to HVM³’s designed capabilities.

Figure 1: The UCIS-Moon spectrometer (left) is identical to the spectrometer inside Lunar Trailblazer’s HVM³ (right).

Property	Value
Spectral range	0.6 – 3.6 μm
Spectral sampling	10 nm
Spatial sampling	50-90 m/pixel* (IFOV ≤ 0.77 mrad)
Field of view	24°
Pixel size	30 μm
Instrument mass	$\leq 14\text{kg}$

*Assumes a 100km Lunar Trailblazer-like orbit; UCIS-Moon orbiter provider and parameters not yet selected

Table 1: UCIS-Moon instrument performance is identical to HVM³.

UCIS-Moon built for an orbiter will use in-hand flight spares that are shared between HVM³ and the UCIS-Moon DALI technology development task. These include a CHROMA detector array from Teledyne, spectrometer mirrors, spectrometer housing, and grating substrates. UCIS-Moon will also re-use ground support equipment that was originally purpose built for HVM³ and the UCIS-Moon-DALI, including calibration and optical alignment equipment [5,6]. The instrument will also leverage significant expertise from key HVM³ team members and mission operational plans originally developed for Lunar Trailblazer.

Science Goals: UCIS-Moon will support two high level science goals. The first is to understand the form, abundance, and distribution of water of the Moon, and improve our understanding of the lunar water cycle. UCIS-Moon will measure the form and abundance of water on sunlit surfaces of the Moon, and will also explore how they vary with time and temperature throughout the lunar day. UCIS-Moon will also determine where and how much ice is trapped in permanently shadowed regions

The second science goal is to enhance the science of landed lunar exploration. UCIS-Moon will map scientifically compelling compositions at the 10s of meter scale, which will guide landing site selection and aid in traverse planning for future robotic and human exploration missions. These data may also be helpful in identifying mineral resources.

Achieving both goals will address high-priority decadal survey science questions.

Status and next steps: NASA is working to identify a future orbiter that could carry UCIS-Moon. Like Lunar Trailblazer, the UCIS-Moon team is planning to have an open policy for community input of targets, a rapid 3 month data release, and quicklooks available within 24-hrs of downlink. The UCIS-Moon team has a strong desire to keep the science of this mission community-focused.

References: [1] NASA press release, <https://www.nasa.gov/news-release/nasa-selects-instruments-for-artemis-lunar-terrain-vehicle/> [2] Fraeman, A.A. et al., (2023) 54th LPS, Abstract #1497 [3] Haag, J.M. et al., (2020) *Proc. SPIE 11504, Imaging Spectrometry XXIV: Applications, Sensors, and Processing*, 1150403 [4] Ehlmann, B.L. et al., (2022), *2022 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, [5] Bender, H.A. et al., (2023), *Proc. SPIE 12688, Imaging Spectrometry XXVI: Applications, Sensors,*

and Processing, 126880J, [5] McKinley, I.M. et al., (2024), *2024 IEEE Aerospace Conference*.